

Brooks Park Project, Fairfield County (39.90057, -82.51620)

Since construction in 2021, the Brooks Park Project's main nutrient benefit has been filtering inflows from Murphy's Run, as well as occasional backflow from Buckeye Lake. In 2024, this Project acted as a nutrient sink for the large inflow volume it captured from Murphy's Run, filtering 11.4 lbs phosphorus per acre. However, the overall nutrient benefit of the Project could be improved by relatively simple design modifications.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is mixed in terms of management. The Project (5 acres of restored wetland) is a flow-through wetland, nuanced by periodic backflow from Buckeye Lake. Water enters from Murphy's Run via a solar-powered pump (maintained, though not actively managed, by a state park staff) or passively through a separate inlet location. The water resides in wetland pools that permanently/seasonally flood before reaching the outflow into Buckeye Lake. There is often backflow from Buckeye Lake into the wetland pools during the summer when the water level in the lake is raised. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as an event in which Murphy's Run stream discharge is greater than 1.55 cubic feet per second. At this threshold, Murphy's Run flows into the wetland. The water level threshold at which Buckeye Lakes backflows into the wetland pools is 889.5 ft, a number inferred based on elevation information in the Project design plans.

Nutrient Retention

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar pumped, flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Maximizing the volume of water that enters the West Pool via pump would increase residence time at the Project and resulting nutrient filtration opportunity.
- Installing a more efficient pump would bring in greater water volume, as researchers have observed the current solar-powered pump moving little to no water.
- Additionally, installing a cement wall between the Main Pool and the Mid-wetland Stream to divert water from the Main Pool to the West Pool before it flows back into the Mid-Wetland Stream would slow down flows from Murphy's Run, increasing residence time of water in the wetland pools and resulting nutrient filtration opportunity. This design modification would still allow for Buckeye Lake backflows to be treated during times of high-water elevation.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.